

CHARACTERISTICS OF TEACHING IN UNIVERSAL
DISTANCE EDUCATION ENVIRONMENT IN DIFFERENT EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS: PROBLEMS, EXPERIENCES, PROSPECTS

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Annotation: *This article provides a methodology for familiarizing with the benefits, prospects, and definition of distance learning technology among various educational institutions. Additionally, the paper considers the problems of distance learning and the conceptual foundations for creating distance courses and types of facilities and modules to improve the position of distance learning between primary and secondary schools. Distance learning has traditionally been reserved for non-traditional students such as full-time workers, military personnel, and non-residents or individuals in remote regions who cannot attend classroom lectures. However, distance learning has become a well-established part of the educational world and trends point to continued growth.*

Keywords: *information technologies, distance learning, social networks, MOOC, artificial intelligence, digital interactive e-books, digital e-learning manuals, and distance learning courses.*

After gaining independence, serious reforms were carried out in the educational system, as in all spheres, the quality of education began to rise. Therefore, using modern information technology and its material and technical base, it is necessary to create electronic textbooks and teaching aids using internet resources and distance learning programs, which are the products of scientific and technical development. To this end, the use of information technologies in improving the quality of general education and training of specialists, the introduction of Information Technologies at the world level into the educational process is also of great importance. At the same time, distance learning is a type of education based on mutual education between teachers and students, which is carried out using telecommunication technologies and Internet resources, which are far from each other. [1, page 2]

Advantages of distance learning. Joining distance learning through social networks is one of the first innovations in this regard, which allows you to be informed, share your results with friends, as well as get acquainted with the achievements of their friends. Some listeners share their thoughts with blogging. [2, page 145] This contributes to the popularity of distance learning among subscribers, as well as to the strengthening of their knowledge for other listeners. Famous foreign universities also offer their own distance courses through the internet. They will be able to study the lectures of professors, Nobel Prize laureates, although those who have graduated from these courses do not have a

diploma of this high education system. It should also be noted that such a type of education is several times cheaper than traditional education. The fact that the modern educational system cannot meet almost all the requirements of the present era is recognized by many scientists and specialists. [3, page 8] One of the main ways to reverse this situation is to involve a wide range of the latest software and technology of modern technological development in the educational system. One such tool is an open distance learning system (MOOC) on digital platforms that allows people to learn full-time education without being separated from production and other everyday tasks.[4, pages 12-24] A few years ago, that is, in the autumn of 2012, the professors of Stanford University Sebastian Trun and Peterigig invited everyone to listen to lectures on artificial intelligence online. Classes are formed only online. The maximum number of lecturers was 2-3 thousand students at the beginning of the semester, although they planned to go to these classes, 160 000 people from 200 countries were enrolled in classes. It is impossible not to emphasize that similar distance learning systems are becoming more complex and qualitative. As the day goes by, more and more experienced teachers and professors want to make their lectures accessible to others in an open way, and these video hands-on videos can be recorded on Youtube and iTunes platforms or apps. One of them, for example, Michael Sendel, professor of political philosophy at Harvard University, became one of the most famous people because of the popularity of the spirituality course called Justice in social networks. It is observed that their joint efforts lead to modern and qualitative education of people living anywhere in the world. These processes show that great importance is attached to the training of personnel for the digital economy.

Several inconveniences can arise in the methods of distance learning and teaching. For some people, distance training seems to be a tedious and generally poor-quality training program. In other words, there are not even those students who continue to relate the teaching with the traditional idea of a face-to-face lesson, where there is the interaction between the teacher and the students. Admittedly, some curricula are specially formulated to attract the attention of students to the programs used in Language Teaching, but some programs are still being brought to the public attention before they are fully completed. This is being pointed out as one of the mistakes made in distance learning.

In addition, distance learning can be very useful for some theoretical disciplines, but in the practical methodology, it can be more difficult to fully study these modules, for example, to study music and several other disciplines.

The role and importance of distance learning system in education archives. In pursuance of the 4th paragraph of Order №526 of the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 30, 2016 "On the organization of the introduction of educational-methodical complexes in electronic education system", it was decided to place and use educational and methodological aids in electronic system (process) of education- Moodle. This creates a lot of opportunities for both teachers and students. The student and the teacher interact through the internet in spatial separation, as the student works more on himself and with the help of other

technologies of the Internet and by constantly communicating with the teacher. The most important thing is that distance learning does not depend on the place, time, the number of students is not limited. During distance learning, the student assimilates independent teaching textbooks, answering control questions. This type of education is considered to be a very convenient system of education for correspondence, special correspondence, qualification courses, as well as for married, adult, and working students.

Prospects of the distance education system. Gradually from the field of education, the squeezing out of a person and the replacement of them by artificial intelligence takes place in our eyes. Proceeding from the above, and in our opinion-in, our opinion-to implementing the rapid and large-scale implementation of digital innovative methods in the educational process in our country, it is necessary to immediately take the following measures:

1. The formation of various types of education in different ways leads to the need for the preparation of digital interactive e-books, electronic manuals, and distance learning courses in particular subjects, involving qualified professors and teachers (including those who have already retired) under the ministries of education (this work is carried out not for free, as it is now, but based on the task of organizing the Republican working Council (Organization or company) for the implementation of these works. At the Republican level, the task is to prepare modern and high-quality digital interactive e-books, digital e-learning manuals, and distance learning courses (or to translate them from foreign languages into Uzbek);

2. To attract to this work all organizations, educational institutions, companies, and leading institutions and universities engaged in the application of information technologies in the country in a mandatory manner;

3. The distance education system, which allows citizens who want to receive secondary and higher education in different areas of Uzbekistan to receive full-time education without being separated from the production and other daily tasks, is developed based on the developed platforms of foreign countries "distance education – MOOC-massive open online courses" organization and their immediate launch. This – if the first creates equal opportunities for all those wishing to receive education, and the second allows significantly less money spent on the education system and, thirdly, creates a very large number of new jobs for young people, young people, which do not require state expenditure;

4. Development of digital interactive e-books and digital manuals for all educational institutions or to indicate the need to use them as a priority task, as well as to develop criteria for determining the rating indicators for the performance of these works;

5. Digital interactive e-books, manuals, computer games related to the field of education, intellectual educational platforms, distance learning systems, programs, and sites, which are important for us, developed and approved abroad, turn them into the Uzbek language, concentrate them on a special Republican fund, place them on the educational portal on the internet and distribute them for use in all educational institutions;

6. It would be desirable to place them on a special educational portal (including on the sites of ministries and educational institutions, libraries, resource centers) so that all students and teachers could use the digital interactive electronic books and educational manuals produced (or translated, adapted) on a Republican scale;

7. Every year, the contest of the best digital interactive books, manuals, launched distance learning platforms and computer games related to education and awarding the winners and summarizing the achieved results to the Republican fund, placing them on the educational portal on the internet and distributing them to all educational institutions for use;

8. Organization of conferences and seminars on digital interactive books, manuals, distance learning platforms, and computer games related to education created in the Republic once a year on the scale of the Republic and regions;

9. Taking into account their development and use of digital interactive electronic books, interactive manuals, and computer games related to education in the assessment of the work Activity Monitor of professors and teachers in educational institutions;

10. Those who have created digital interactive books, distance learning platforms, and electro teaching aids would have a positive impact on the increase in their number and quality in thoroughly rewarding both financially and morally.

In conclusion, I can say that distance learning has created great opportunities for all schoolchildren, especially students. Now schoolchildren do not have to personally attend the academic center or universities every day, but through new technologies, they can follow the lesson from home. The learning process is also fully adapted to digital technologies, and distance learning is creating new conveniences in every way. Distance education today is necessary not only for educational institutions but also for large enterprises and institutions in today's globalization process, which plays an important role in training, retraining, maintaining a high level of their knowledge and skills. Distance education is not only necessary for educational institutions today, but also in today's globalization process, large enterprises and institutions play an important role in training, retraining, maintaining a high level of knowledge and skills. There is an opportunity to increase the level of general knowledge of the population and the quality of this knowledge by applying distance education. It will be possible to meet the needs of all types of the population for Voluntary Education.

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